

Best-practice workflow to indicate appropriate structural geological conditions to assist future exploration campaigns

The HyAfrica project aims to investigate the potential of naturally occurring hydrogen (H₂) found in specific geological settings across Africa. The study outlines the geological and structural conditions most commonly associated with hydrogen occurrences observed at the Earth's surface. It highlights key indicators of potential natural hydrogen, beginning with surface-level signs of hydrogen flux, followed by geological features such as reservoirs and traps. Finally, it explores possible hydrogen sources located deeper within the crust and mantle.

WorkFlow

This best-practice workflow (Figure 1) considers key geomorphological, geochemical, and geological features from the surface downward. Although this order contrasts with the typical migration path of hydrogen, which moves from deep sources upward to the surface, confidence in identifying significant factors generally decreases with depth. As a result, the workflow follows a pattern from high to low confidence, aligning with the steps typically followed in exploring potential natural hydrogen resources. The workflow is illustrated in Fig. 1 and covers four key stages: 1) Near-surface factors, 2) Shallow-level factors, 3) Moderate-level factors, and 4) Deep-level factors.

Figure 1 Best-practice workflow to indicate appropriate structural geological conditions to assist future exploration campaigns.

1. Surface and near-surface expressions of hydrogen flux

Surface hydrogen occurrences identified in the HyAfrica project have been linked to circular or sub-circular depressions (SCDs) at the Earth's surface. These features, known locally as fairy circles, Carolina bays (in North Carolina, USA), or pans, are commonly associated with natural hydrogen emissions. SCDs, near hydrogen occurrences, are likely formed due to rock alteration caused by hydrogen flow near the surface (see Figure 2).

Figure 2 Geomorphic depressions with H₂ soil-gas measurements

This strong connection between hydrogen flux and SCDs enables cost-effective target identification using satellite imagery, digital elevation models, and vegetation indices derived from infrared data (See Figure 3).

Figure 3 Utilisation in arid landscapes for the detection of SCDs.

2. Shallow-level geology

Shallow-level hydrogen accumulation relies on effective traps such as tight sandstones, shales, evaporites, or dolerite sills, which prevent upward migration by advection despite hydrogen's high diffusivity. Structural features like gentle folding may aid accumulation, while excessive faulting can compromise seals, though faults can also influence hydrogen flow by modifying pathways (see Figure 4), impeding cross-fault flow, or acting as conduits through interconnected fractures.

Figure 4 Map indicating sub-parallel arrangement between the pans and faults in part of the South African HyAfrica target area.

3. Moderate-level geology

Moderate-level hydrogen systems often involve weakly deformed Neoproterozoic to Phanerozoic strata acting as effective seals above hydrogen sources in deeper, faulted Precambrian rocks such as greenstones, ophiolites, or Banded Iron Formations. Unconformities commonly separate these contrasting layers, while in some deep basins, thermogenic processes in organic-rich Phanerozoic rocks can also generate hydrogen.

4. Deep-level geology

Deep-level hydrogen production relies on water circulation and geothermal energy, with serpentinisation being a key process that occurs in mafic and ultramafic rocks at depths of 7 to 10 km and temperatures between 200°C and 350°C. Source rocks linked to this process include mafic intrusions, greenstone belts, ophiolites, and Banded Iron Formations, with known examples in Mali, South Africa, Finland, France, the USA, and Brazil.